

TEACHING PHYSICS WITH INTERACTIVE METHODS AMONG STUDENTS**TUYCHIEV NURBEK BURKHON OGLI**

Teacher of physics

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Annotation: This in the article physics science in education new pedagogical from technologies of use advantages about thought held. The purpose of using new pedagogic technologies in physics education is to bring the learner to the center of the lesson process, to move students away from mere memorization and voluntary repetition of educational materials, to develop their independent and creative activities, and to turn them into active participants of the lesson.

Key words: Physics, new pedagogical technology, rule, formula, method, interactive methods, interactive, laws of physics.

INTRODUCTION. The 21st century spiritual, educational, economic-social, technical and technological spheres of our society are being gradually reformed. Especially the purpose of educational processes is to educate a free person based on pedagogic technologies.

The process is not easy. It is necessary to transform the educational system, which is being built voluntarily and is implemented in practice, into a strictly scientifically based pedagogic system. Improving the content of watering this process with the spirit of universal and national values is one of the main tasks of creative teachers.

In order to increase the quality and efficiency of education, the main task of the program is to update the content of education, to regularly improve the mental and intellectual development of the young generation, and to provide a new model of education from a scientific pedagogical point of view. Use of interactive methods in teaching physics. 2004 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In the decision of July 9, 2004-2009 "On measures for the implementation of the state nationwide program for the development of school education", there are 5 main priorities, and the implementation of its paragraphs 2, 3 and 4 is generally among directors of educational schools and teachers of all subjects

Physics teachers also have huge tasks. This, of course, requires physics teachers to have a creative approach to their profession and to teach students to study and be observant. There are many methods and methods of achieving this, the teacher should follow the method of independent and accurate performance of the tasks assigned to the students, regardless of using any of these methods. Interactive methods are based on the active relationship between the teacher and the student, mutual understanding. The main goal of introducing interactive methods into the educational process is to organize the cooperation of the teacher and the student in the lesson, regardless of the form of the lesson, wherever it is taught.

Is to achieve. The teacher should attract students to relevant problems in the lesson, activate their actions and ensure their mastery as a result. The task of knowledge in the educational process problematic questions occupy the main place in the setting. They each create problematic situations put according to what methods. The question of knowledge is at a certain level for students it is necessary to be difficult, to show the limitations of their existing knowledge and at the same time, to be able to do it, that is, it is necessary to take into account the dependence of perception on life experience and the extent to which theoretical knowledge

is acquired. Interactivity is the interaction between the teacher and the student. The action of interaction during the transition to the stage of improvement of cooperation activities an increase from assessment to self-assessment occurs. This process is one of the most important factors indicating the dynamics of cooperation. Group students are divided into small groups of 4-5 people for training based on cooperative learning technology. It should be noted that there are strong, medium and weak students in each group. Because it should be ensured that the teams are equally strong. The placement of desks in the classroom helps small groups work. Students sit in a circle and look directly at each other. The advantage of this situation is that students can communicate directly with each other enables students to exchange ideas quickly and find solutions quickly as a result. It should also be noted that in this case, during the discussion, the weaker students play the role of the learner. That is, they listen to the opinion of high-level students and get the necessary knowledge from them and tries to join them.

RESULTS: As a result, the growth of low-level students in the group is achieved. During the preparation for the training session, it is planned which part of the subject will be explained by the teacher and which part will be performed by the students. Based on the purpose of the lesson, the tasks assigned to each student should be clear. So questions should be asked based on the student's level. Let's see what advantages it has. For example, when a weaker student is given a more difficult question, it is known that he will not be able to find the answer to the question, and as a result, his self-confidence will decrease and his interest in science will decrease. If we ask him a question appropriate to his level, he will be able to answer it (to the best of his ability) and his love for science will increase again. But it is not necessary to ask simple questions to a weak student every time, because he will get used to simple questions and will not want to bother with difficult questions. Therefore, it is necessary to give more difficult questions to weak students from time to time. This keeps them motivated. Now as for strong students, it is not good to ask them easy questions because they find these questions boring and as a result, they develop boredom and apathy towards the subject. Therefore, it is necessary to ask them more difficult questions. If the task consists of answering questions about a new topic, then a difficult question will be given to a strong student. The answer given by the student is answered by one of the participants of the group

He checks the book and says that it is wrong. Then the student writes the answer in the notebook if the answer is correct. The student must then provide evidence and examples to support the answer. In this process, almost all students become participants in the process. He answers himself. If it is correct, his joy will increase infinitely, if the answer is incorrect, he will know the correct answer from the child who read the correct answer from the book and the correct conclusion from his mistake. After that, the students will be able to exchange places, that is, the person giving an opinion to the question will give the answer to the question from the book to the reader, and in turn, the correct answer will be given to the question from the book. At the end of the discussion, the students in the small group should answer all the questions and present them to the whole group.

CONCLUSION

Today, the interest and attention to the use of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, If students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by

themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. Accordingly, the teaching of physics topics in this subject in innovative ways helps students to understand the subject on a scientific basis, to think independently. In this process, the teacher is a condition for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual creates and at the same time performs the function of management and guidance. Pupils become the main figure in the educational process. Innovative technologies are the introduction of innovations and changes to the pedagogical process and teacher's and pupil's activities. Interactive methods are considered a component of the educational content. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and students. In the opinion of teachers, researchers, and practitioners who study the issues and problems of pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is only related to information technology. It is defined as the use of computers, distance learning or various techniques that are necessary to be used in the teaching process. In our opinion, the main basis of pedagogical technology depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal. That is, every educational technology used in the teaching process to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal can organize cooperative activities between the teacher and the student, and both can achieve a positive result. If the teacher-students can think independently, work positively, search, analyze, draw their own conclusions, evaluate themselves, the group, and the group, the teacher creates opportunities and conditions for such activities. takes in our opinion, this is the study process.

Each lesson, subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is directed and designed in advance based on the needs of the student. and is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a guaranteed result. How the teacher and the student achieve the result from the goal it is up to them to choose the technology, because the main goal of both parties is to achieve a specific result, in which the technology used is chosen depending on the level of knowledge of the students, the nature of the group, the situation, for example, working with a computer to achieve the result it is necessary, maybe a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology will be needed, these depend on the teacher and the student. grouping, contests, brainstorming, discussion and other methods that we teach to students in accordance with the topic will increase their activity. When dividing into groups, it would be appropriate to assign equally excellent students to each group. This situation causes the average reader, who does not know how to think freely, to move. Causes a positive impact on the group. The more students are interested in the lesson, the more their knowledge will increase is to increase students' knowledge using different methods.

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